

HISTORY, TYPES AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF MUSIC EDITOR PROGRAMS

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The new generation of knowledge Along with the development of modern scientific techniques and information technologies, the methods of obtaining and teaching quality knowledge are also changing in all directions.

Since the second half of the 20th century, the development of information technologies has rapidly entered all spheres of human life with its own practical solutions. This process has certainly not bypassed representatives of the music industry. Starting from the third quarter of the 20th century, computer music editors began to actively implement photographic and publishing operations. The first notations were introduced into the score editor program "Score" in the late 1970s. Since it was created on the basis of notation tools used in the computer era, it is still used by some publishers. Also noteworthy is the music editor "Music Construction Set", developed in 1984. Some researchers consider it the forerunner of modern computer music editors.

Modern programs for notation allow you to edit, create and play music sheets using a variety of input methods (using a mouse, a computer keyboard, a MIDI keyboard connected to a computer, or MIDI files). In addition, editors have the ability to listen to the notes being entered using a software synthesizer. However, this sound is largely indistinguishable from the real voice, since such music programs are not designed to be played through a high-quality MIDI device. Professional music editing programs have the ability to perform all the preliminary work (from entering notes to designing) and prepare a musical work of any complexity and direction for printing.

Some music notation programs have the ability to recognize scanned music text. However, this feature requires very advanced software and technical processes, even in the best music notation programs.

Music notation programs offer great opportunities for importing from files in other formats (MIDI, MusicXML, NIFF, etc.) and exporting (JPEG, TIFF, PDF, MIDI, MP3, Karaoke, Flash).

A problem for musicians is the incompatibility of various note editors. For transposition, it is necessary to use the MIDI format. In this case, most of the useful information, including all design work, is completely lost. Several

attempts have been made to create a universal format for musical text. Currently, the MusicXML format is widespread.

It should be noted that, despite the great competition among developers of music score editors, to this day there are well-known professional music score editors such as "Finale", "Sibelius", "MagicScore". Among the existing music score editors, the best music score editor developed in the CIS is considered to be the "MagicScore" music score editor. It has a Russian interface and supports the developer's certificate.

The unique "Music Notation Software" program for the "MS Word" text editor and the simplified version of the "Music Making" note editor are designed for the "MS Word" text editor, which allows you to create methodological applications for music education, writing books and articles, as well as fully exchange information between classical note editors. can be implemented. The notes written using this method can be read, edited and directly displayed in the text editor "MS Word" by users without any additional applications.

When talking about note entry programs, it is impossible not to mention programs for scanning and recognizing paper notes, saving them in a format for later editing, continuing to work with notes, and exporting them. Of the English and American programs, note recognition programs such as "Sharpie", "SmartScore", "PhotoScore" are more accurate. The best of these was the program SharryEye, which was published by the most famous computer magazine in Germany, "Deutschland C'T", in a series of independent surveys. In addition, this program can be used completely free of charge for 30 days without any restrictions.

The SmartScore note recognition programs are interesting for their special versions of SmartScore X Piano and SmartScore Guitar, although their functionality is limited (2 note sound rows for the first program and the first for the second), they provide high quality note recognition, the second program also recognizes tablature, chords and recursion, the price of these special versions is the same as that of SharpEye, so within these limitations If you can recognize musical notation, these programs can also be a good choice.

The note recognition software "SmartScore", "PhotoScore" has a beautiful appearance, the quality of note recognition, and the ease of use of the three programs "SharpeEye", "SmartScore" and "PhotoScore" are on a par. Therefore, under conditions of technological equality, the price factor provides "SharpeEye" with a more attractive interface and there is no doubt that the choice in its direction will be more reasonable.

Musical graphics have evolved from a rough definition of pitch to its modern form, with the loudness of notes and other parameters used to determine their duration and performance. However, modern notation editors continue to evolve, as they are used in many digital photography products. At the same time, new methods are available to solve the problem of identifying musical works. In the future, we will probably witness the emergence of new, more advanced music notation systems.

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